

TEACHING ENGLISH WITH ACTIVITIES

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Roziboeva Tabassum Ma'murjanovna

an English teacher of Andijan region, Qo'rg'ontepa district, school 3

Annotation: *This article is about communicative activities such as those described below can be used successfully with many class levels.*

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Nowadays proficiency in English is an absolute advantage, since it allows a person to achieve success in various fields of activity, as well as in situations of interpersonal communication. One of the components of a successful command of English, in our opinion, is the communicative competence, or, in other words, the ability to clearly formulate your thoughts, understand the interlocutor and achieve the task of communication. Communicative activities include any activities that encourage and require a learner to speak with and listen to other learners, as well as with people in the program and community. Communicative activities have real purposes: to find information, break down barriers, talk about self, and learn about the culture. In our opinion, the most effective way to develop communicative competence is to use communication games in English lessons. Learning through play involves setting a specific task, within the framework of which students are more motivated to use the necessary language tools. Also, communication games are built on situations of everyday communication and can serve as a preparation for real communication. Finally, by communicating with each other in the context of the game, students overcome psychological barriers, which contributes to the development of not only language skills, but also personal qualities. The techniques of the communicative technique are used in communicative games, in which students solve communicative and cognitive tasks by means of the foreign language being studied. Therefore, the main goal of communication games is to organize foreign language communication in the course of solving a given communicative task or problem. In our lessons, we actively use the following communication activities:

Activity 1."Appointment". The goal of the game: to make an appointment . Speech patterns used in the game: Can you/ Would you like to come to ... on...? How/What about...? I'd love to. I'm sorry I'm ...-ing. Vocabulary: cinema, theatre, concert, restaurant, disco, bowling alley, cafe; days of the week, times.

How to play: Give each student a card with the days of the week, so-called diaries, and write on the board a list of seven different places, for example, cinema, theater, concert, restaurant, disco, bowling alley, and cafe. Each student must decide where they will go on each day of the week. They can visit only one place in one evening and only with one friend. The goal of the game is to make appointments and write it down in a diary. When they complete their diaries, they should meet with their friend and discuss their entertainment program for the evening.

Activity 2."Food ". Students are offered 5-6 thematically related nouns and 4-5 adjectives that convey their possible qualities. For example, to nouns on the topic "Food" you can choose the adjectives "sweet", "bitter" and so on.

Activity 3."There is/are or the question Have you got...?". Before the game, take a bag and put in it 8 different items related to vocabulary on a specific topic, such as animals, school supplies. Show it to the children and explain that they have the opportunity to ask 20 questions to guess all the items in the bag. For example, Is there a rubber in the bag? Have you got a dog in the bag? If the student guesses the subject, then it must be taken out of the bag and shown. Children win if they have guessed all the items, while asking no more than 20 questions. During the game, you must record the number of questions asked.

Activity 4."Professions". Write the names of various professions on stickers (for example, teacher, waiter, doctor, vet, etc.) and attach one of them to the back of each student. At the same time, children should not know what their profession is. Explain to the children that they should walk around the classroom and ask each other questions in turn to learn their profession. For example: Do I work at school? Do I wear a uniform? Do I help people? Do I like animals? Thus, the effectiveness, fun and variety of communication games makes them an indispensable tool for teaching English and leaves room for the imagination of every teacher. Based on the above, it can be argued that the main goal of modern language education is to prepare students for the communication process. In this regard, the use of a communicative approach in teaching a foreign

language is very relevant in overcoming the language barrier in the process of real communication.

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